

SEVERE PRE-ECLAMPSIA AND ITS TREATMENT BY THE EYES OF A REANIMATIST

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ANNOTATION: The paper presents an analysis of data on the course of pregnancy in women with severe preeclampsia against the background of extragenital pathology and methods of its treatment with the participation of resuscitators. The factors influencing the occurrence of preeclampsia, the course of pregnancy and its complications, ways of effectively reducing pressure and stabilizing the patient while maintaining pregnancy were studied.

Key words: preeclampsia, risk groups, BMI, fetal biometrics, extragenital pathology of the mother, first aid, outcomes of pregnancy and childbirth.

Relevance. Hypertensive disorders during pregnancy are one of the most severe complications of pregnancy and still remain an unsolved mystery that overshadows the birth of a new person. This complication is characterized by a high frequency, especially in recent years (2009 and later) and accounts for 17-24% of the total number of pregnant women and women in childbirth [1,2]. Delivery, eliminating the cause of the disease, does not eliminate the mechanisms of progression of changes in organs and systems associated with the main links in the pathogenesis of hypertensive conditions. In women who have undergone this complication of pregnancy, chronic kidney disease and hypertension are formed, leading to disability, and the quality of life decreases.

Literature sources indicate that the treatment of hypertensive disorders during pregnancy remains largely symptomatic [3,4,5]. Opinions about the timing and method of delivery of such pregnant women also remain controversial. The need for the development and implementation of optimal examination methods, treatment regimens, methods and timing of delivery of severe preeclampsia remains obvious.

Purpose of the study. To study the features of the course of pregnancy in women with severe preeclampsia and to identify effective ways to stabilize patients while maintaining pregnancy.

Materials and research methods. 60 pregnant women were examined in early and late gestation, who were in the obstetric department of the multidisciplinary clinic No. 1 of the Samarkand Medical University. Pregnant women were divided into 3 groups: Group I - 20 women whose pregnancy was complicated by preeclampsia in the period from 22 to 30 weeks. Group II - 20 women whose pregnancy was complicated by preeclampsia in a period of 30 weeks or more. III group 20 women with normal pregnancy. The average age of the surveyed was 26.3 ± 2.8 years.

For the examination of pregnant women, general clinical, functional, laboratory research methods, the results of additional research methods (ultrasound feto- and placentometry, dopplerometry, CTG) were used, which were entered into the individual cards of the examined. Results: In the first two groups, pregnant women complained of nausea, vomiting 1-2 times a

day, general weakness, fatigue. In 10% of patients of the first and 40% of the second groups, there was an excess of body weight of varying severity, and in the second group, BMI was statistically significantly higher ($p < 0.01$).

As a result of the analysis of the anamnesis data, the closest relatives of the examined women (50.0%) had diseases of the cardiovascular (hypertension, NCD, myocardial infarction, etc.), urinary (CLD, pyelonephritis, renal failure, etc.), endocrine (DM) systems, as well as complications during pregnancies. Among the patients of groups I and III there were no diseases against which a severe form of preeclampsia could develop. In the II group of examined patients, a large proportion in the structure of extragenital pathology had disorders of the cardiovascular system in the form of neurocirculatory dystonia. Only in 8 (40%) patients from the first group, pregnancy was complicated by placental insufficiency.

There were 34 (56.6%) primigravidas, 26 (43.3%) women were recurrent. The course of this pregnancy in the general group of patients was complicated by vomiting of pregnant women in 20% of patients, the threat of termination of pregnancy - in 45% of patients, anemia - in 65.0%. The Zangemeister triad occurred only in 28.3% of pregnant women with preeclampsia. More often, two symptoms of preeclampsia were expressed (61.7%), sometimes only one symptom (monosymptomatic preeclampsia), which was mainly observed in pregnant women with preeclampsia against the background of neurocirculatory dystonia (in 10% of cases).

Analyzing the results of ultrasound biometry, we found that in most cases (80.8%), the size of the fetus corresponded to the gestational age. It is noteworthy that in subgroups with preeclampsia, a large number of studies noted a lag in the size of the fetus during biometrics: 20% in group I and 15% in group II ($p > 0.05$). Ultrasonic placentography in 56 (93.3%) - the placenta was located on the anterior and lateral walls of the uterus, while 16 (28.5%) of them had low placentation. On the back wall of the uterus, the placenta was localized in 4 (6.67%) of the examined pregnant women. The thickness of the placenta was within the normative values, and only in 5 (8.33%) cases we noted a thin placenta. When assessing the degree of maturity of the placenta, its premature maturation was noted in 12 (20%) examined. In 3 (5%) studies, we found placental cysts, in 1 (1.6%), a single umbilical artery was noted. In 10 (16.6%) examined patients, hyperechoic inclusions were found in the placenta (they were regarded as petrificates). Noteworthy is the high frequency of oligohydramnios in groups I and II of the examined (30% and 20%, respectively).

Patients of the first two groups received treatment according to the protocol with the inclusion of magnesia therapy and magnesium preparations, in addition, the patients were under constant control. After 4 hours, a third showed a positive trend with a decrease in blood pressure. In these patients, laboratory screening parameters also returned to normal within a few days.

In 35% of patients from the first group and 20% of the second, despite the treatment, the pressure remained high. After a 12-hour observation, it was decided to deliver. All patients were delivered surgically.

Conclusion. Thus, such extragenital diseases as NCD and chronic pyelonephritis most often contributed to the development of severe forms of preeclampsia and eclampsia. Violation of the development of fetal parameters by ultrasound was detected to a greater extent in patients of the second group.

Magnesia therapy and standard treatment proved to be effective in a third of patients. But in 35% of patients from the first group and 20% of the second, despite the treatment, the pressure remained high and required surgical delivery.

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